

A STUDY ON INFLUENCER MARKETING OF PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

Influencer marketing is a novel way of promoting brands and products. The social media stars make use of their fan base and convert them into potential buyers. The social media influencers are more active in different social media platforms like Youtube, Instagram, and Facebook and they market the personal care products which are used for self-grooming, to look beauty and some cosmetics to their followers. In recent years urban and semi-urban consumers of personal care products in India have become more conscious about how they appear, smell, and how natural and organic the products are. The marketers identified huge market prospects for costly and quality beauty and cosmetic products and so to reach the target audience they have chosen this social media influencer as a new marketing channel. During the covid-19 pandemic, the rise in usage of the internet and Smartphone users results to bring more and more new social media users. The two factors, sales promotion of costly products and drastic growth of social media followers become an opportunity to create a niche market for many new brands and existing brands in the personal care products domain, these products are positioned in the minds of social media followers using different strategy by the social media celebrities. In this article we are going to discuss 1. what is influencer marketing? , 2. Who are social media influencers? , 3. How do they influence the buying decision of personal care products during the pandemic? And how the influencer becomes an opinion leader? From this study, we can come to know how an optimistic approach has been made to market the products in critical and undesirable situations.

Keywords: Influencer marketing, social media influencers, personal care products.

INTRODUCTION

In the Indian economy retail sector plays a significant role and in that, the retail market's fast-moving consumer goods (FMCG) occupies a huge size of it. FMCG is also one of the largest sectors and it is in the place of 4th among other sectors. The market size of the FMCG sector is about US Dollar 110 billion in 2020 which was expected to double by 2025 that is US Dollar 220 billion. From this FMCG sector, we have taken personal care products as the specific domain for our study because it covers almost 50% sales revenue of FMCG. (IBEF, 2021) The personal care industry in India is a rising star due to the beauty-conscious of individuals and increase in the disposal income. (*India Beauty and Personal Care Market Outlook, 2021*). And also there is a change in the preference and demand of personal care products by the customer; they have started to pick high-quality products after the first wave of the covid-19 pandemic. (Reetesh Dhingra, 2021) During pandemic periods 2020 and 2021 there is an increase in the count of internet users to 61% in comparison with 21% in 2017 (Khanna, 2021) This leads to an increase in usage of social media between 2020 and 2021 to 78 million users that is 21% growth. (Social Media Day 2021: History, Significance and How It Emerged as a Ray of Hope amid Covid, 2021) This situation created an opportunity for social media influencers to grow rapidly during the pandemic. The article will depict the outlook of influencers and their position in personal care product marketing.

OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this study are the following

- To bring out the key factors that affect influencer marketing of personal care products.
- To examine the marketing effects of influencers during the pandemic.
- To know how influencers affect the purchase intention of personal care products

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The literature review method is used to study social media influencers and to examine their impact on consumer behavior and purchase intention. This article highlights the factors affecting influencer marketing of personal care products. The study explores the views and perspectives of different authors about influencer marketing and personal care products from previous research. Secondary data are collected from various sources like journals, research articles, and web pages. Based on the information collected, we examine how influencers market personal care products during pandemics?, what factors should be given more attention?.

PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

Personal care products are primarily used to maintain an individual's hygiene and physical appearance. Personal care products are part of fast-moving consumer goods and occupy a major portion of its sales volume. Personal care products are classified based on their applications into the following they are hair care products, oral care products, skincare products, and fragrances. Haircare products include hair oil, shampoo, hair conditioner. Oral care products comprise toothpaste, toothbrush, mouth wash, and other oral hygiene products. Skincare products include bath soap, face wash, body lotion, and other beauty products.

SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS

Social media influencers are individuals who have many loyal followers in social media and recommend some products to those audiences and induce them to buy. (*9 of the Biggest Social Media Influencers on Instagram*, 2021) There are different types of social media followers based on the number of followers they have, Mega-influencers are at the top with more than 1 million followers and these types of influencers are celebrities in different fields like the film industry, sportspeople, and music artists. Mega-influencers mostly promote high-value brands and products. In the next level macro-influencers with followers between 40,000 and 1 million followers, they also celebrities but not so much famous compared to mega influencers and micro-influencers come next who have followers in the range of 1000 to 40,000. Micro-influencers are those who promote the niche products from their own experience with those products. Nano-influencers are with very limited followers of 1000. (Geyser, 2022)

SOCIAL MEDIA INFLUENCERS DURING PANDEMIC

Covid-19 pandemic has made the marketers understand and make use of social media influencers for product placement. Social media influencers utilized this opportunity to market the products and increased the sale of products. (Ghosh, 2021) Brands have used influencer marketing as a tool to promote during this pandemic situation. Marketers are more conscious about selecting social media influencers to promote the brands and products because they need more efficient and effective influencers who are creative, informative, and more attached with their followers, This can be helpful to the brands to connect and interact with customers through social media. Influencers improve brand engagement by recommending the products after their own experience. (Francisco et al., 2021) The purchasing pattern and behavior of the consumers have changed due to the promotion activities by social media influencers. Consumers are more influenced by the product reviews of the influencers and it increased sales volume and value of beauty products. The pandemic situation made most of the firms use influencer marketing to interact with their customer actively and get feedback from them, this helped them to maintain the customer satisfaction level. (Youngsil Ma & Ki Han Kwon, 2021) During the pandemic, social media platforms are utilized effectively to influence the consumers' decision-making processes by social media influencers. Many organizations deployed influencers to strengthen their brands and make them aware of their products. The importance of influencer marketing is grown during the pandemic. Influencers share details about how to use the product and their experience, reviews on that product with the followers, which in turn influence the buying behavior of consumers. (Mason et al., 2021)

FACTORS AFFECTING INFLUENCER MARKETING

The three key aspects of influencer and follower, bonding are: one is that the influencer inspires the followers by providing new concepts and ideas to the followers, two is that followers identify more similarities with the influencer in terms of interests and tastes, and three is that the influencer provides informative content for the audience. (Ki et al., 2020) The higher and fixed congruence between the influencer and consumer and also higher congruence with the product by influencer leads to high congruence among product and consumer, the attitude exhibited by the consumer towards the product is also favorable (Belanche et al., 2021) According to the study conducted by (Argyris et al., 2020) the stronger follower and influencer relation lead to increase in follower and brand engagement and so the influencers should have a good rapport with the followers by replying to their comments for the posts in social media and increase the connectivity and attachment with them. The marketer should consider the benefits of using both celebrity influencers and small scale influencers (macro & micro-influencer) during the promotion of the products because celebrity influencer has the feature of a large number of followers and the small scale influencers are easy to access by followers and more active in social media, so the different combination of influencers types can be used to reach the target audience for effective promotion. (Campbell & Farrell, 2020) The opinion of influencer who creates a good trust and friendly relationship with the followers are more valued and considered by followers to engage with the brand they referred (Argyris et al., 2020) Since influencer marketing is in the initial stage the companies should choose the right type of influencer that fit their products since every type doesn't suit the particular product. Disclosure of sponsored content in the right manner will bring out a good impression on influencers and brand promotion. (Ye et al., 2021) The promotion of cosmetic products through influencer marketing is affected by different factors they are physical appearance & attractiveness, trustworthiness, and credibility of the information. Familiarity and friendly relationships among social media influencers and followers are established with the help of good interaction and this makes influencers to be trustworthy. The credibility of content is a crucial thing to convert a viewer into a buyer. (Xiao et al., 2018) Audiences' intention to purchase the products marketed by social media influencers depends more on the two factors they are credibility and parasocial relationship. The impact of parasocial interaction on purchase intention of beauty products is higher compared to the credibility of the products. (Sokolova & Kefi, 2020) The consumers' attention and parasocial relationship are improved while using Youtube compared to other social media platforms. Interactive features in Youtube helped social media influencers to enhance their relationship with audiences. The most vital thing for influencer marketing is to choose the right social media platform and Youtube is an appropriate choice for promoting beauty and skincare products. (Lee & Lee, 2021) Social media influencers can build trust among the followers using their expertise on products, authentic and reliable content. If there is a stronger relationship between influencer and audience then the effect of authenticity and its role on trust build is lesser, the expertise of influencers is recognized by followers only after frequent interaction between them and so interactivenss is crucial to build trust. (Kim & Kim, 2021)

INFLUENCER MARKETING OF PERSONAL CARE PRODUCTS

Social media influencers changed the way of promoting cosmetic products to customers and turned into a social relationship with followers, this method will soon replace the traditional way of just transactional relationships with buyers and sellers. Influencers market customized cosmetic products for customers of different demographics and these types of products are not available in retailer shops. customer repeated purchase is gained through person-to-person interaction and personalized products play a vital role in increasing the sale of cosmetic products. (Suresh et al., 2016) Influencer marketing is gaining popularity since it can reach a vast amount of target audiences in a short period. Social media influencers position the beauty products by sharing their first-hand experience with followers which makes influencers associate more with them. Detailed explanation about the beauty and cosmetic products and their knowledge in the products attracts more audiences and this induces as a stimulus to buy the products. Purchase intention of

audiences toward beauty products is mostly influenced by the visual experience of social media influencers. (Rosara & Luthfia, 2020) The firms are in a situation to cope with crucial competitions and to mitigate the effect of rivalry in the beauty product business they have adapted influencer marketing. Every market player needs to outperform others in this digital era by using social media to position the brand in the minds of audiences and engage with customers. Social media influencers use their popularity to create a good brand image about existing beauty product brands in the market and sometimes to make aware of new beauty brands. Social media influencers reduce the effort of the customer to search for information about personal care products. The expertise and experience of influencers on personal care products are very useful for customers to evaluate the product and to decide whether to buy or not. The followers' trust in influencers, the credibility of information given by influencers, and the influencer's expertise on personal care products are important variables for influencer marketing. (Nagori, 2020)

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

We learned from this study that influencer marketing depends on a variety of factors. First and foremost is choosing the proper social media platform to promote the specific product and, second, choosing the right kind of influencers to promote the personal care products. Credibility, authentic content, repeated interaction, expertise, and trust are the factors that encourage audience members to make purchases. Individuals' suggestions and feedback on personal care products are brought to marketers' attention through influencer marketing. As a result, consumers and marketers can communicate effectively and it helps to acquire and retain more customers.

CONCLUSION

To market the products, firms have approached the pandemic situation in a challenging manner. They, therefore, employed social media to communicate about their products and to learn about customers' needs. By creating trust in the brand through social media influencers, marketers were able to promote personal care products and they have become an opinion leaders by exposing their expertise on personal care products to an audience. This informative content of influencers on social media has a significant influence on the purchase intention of audiences about personal care products.

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